

Transforming Dalit Identity: Education can Empower Dalit

Sanjai Kumar

PhD. Research Scholar
M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

Dr Reena Mittal

MA(Eng.), PhD, MBA
Asso. Prof. and Head (Research Guide)
M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

Abstract

Dalit literature flourished being the mainstream in Indian context with the successful translation of Marathi Dalit writings. The term Dalit first used at the first conference of Maharashtra Dalit Sahitya Sangh. Dalit literature which was emerged in 1960s was the literature of downtrodden backward and disgraced people who were ignored or embellished the expert in upper-class society. they were subjugated by such people since a long time. Around 1960 the Dalit Panthers revisited and embrace the idea of Babasaheb. They Expressed there is basement to the Gandhian philosophy of Indian nationalism to start a new social movement.

Focusing the importance of Dalit literature Arundhati Roy has observed "I do believe that in India be practice a form of apartheid, which goes an unnoticed by the rest of the world." The contemporary Indian literature had an amazing specialty to overlook the real brutality and ugliness of the society in which we were living. Even after more than seventy years of independent India untouchability is still prevailed in the society.

There is hardly any change can be seen in the condition of such communities and segregation in schools and colleges and other places. I am sharing access to education for marginalized subaltern of India has been the greatest challenges for Indian government. There has been the number of reasons that's why Dalit community suffers from low rates of literary and basic education. These people have a long experienced and consistent denial to education since 1980s.

Keywords: Discriminate, Ugliness Challenges, Prevail.

Introduction:

They occupy 16% of the total population of India but still struggling for identity and proper space in this rigid society. Several Dalits converted their religion to avoid this hateful caste system. In some places a little bit financial support provided in case of changing their religion. This is not the permanent solution of the problem. It is only a way to escape from reality. Education is the only medium for them to receive honor and respect in the society. It is more powerful tool to win the world.

Discrimination based on caste works as a barrier in the process of Dalit and empowerment. If we talk about some official analysis Ent which indicate that four out of five female teachers and three out of four main teachers are only from Brahman and rest upper cast. They are responsible to spread caste system. Being the part of the education system, these Brahmin often transmitted this Evil on school level.

There are several examples where the teachers motivated and discourage Dalit students, while to the upper-class student they are incredibly supportive. Discrimination inside the educational Institute affects the innocent mind setup of the creator of the world. They have new dreams and expectations, before knowing the reality of the world in which they are living. The world is no longer fair level to them in terms of class consciousness. They always realize degradation and humiliation.

Importance of education

Education is an essential part of human life. It enables him to face and stand still, in adverse situation. It designs the character and improves the personality of a person. It developed certain qualities of head and heart in a human being. Education increases knowledge and subside the wrong assumption. The most important fact about education is it never discriminates between Dalit and Brahmin.

Now we switch on towards other aspect of education. It proves and effective tool to the subjugated, downtrodden people of the society. They were for away the

reach of this gift of goddess Sarasvati, who imparted to everyone without any distinction. If we discuss in the present context education is the only medium to empower marginals. Number of Dalits is getting empowered by education. Some prominent authors like Saran Kumar limbale, the outcast Lakshman Mane and Om Prakash Valmiki' joothan it is also the depiction of struggle for education at the beginning he was not admitted in the school but later when his father requested to Tyagi to allow him to get admission in the school.

During his schooling he faced number of difficulties, he was not permitted to sit on the proper place, and he sat on the floor at the distinct place. He was always tortured for being a Dalit. The upper-class children called him by his caste. In such advert situation he got education. We people are aware about his present status. Education is a key to success. It empowers the marginalized so they can uplift their way of living and may have respect in the society. Today's world is the world of knowledge.

Those who are excellent in the field are dominating the society. They are the real master; they can manipulate the things according to their will. The world is progressing in the field of science and technology, so it increases the desire in people to use more sources. It is very necessary to the people of India that at least they should get the basic education. At the same the knowledge gap between privileged marginalized has been increased. Knowledge and quality education both are available for subjugated people in India. Exuberance of knowledge and prosperity remain with only selected people of society.

“India has one third of world's illiterates. Forty six percent of our people have not reached the portals education (2001 census -296.2 Million) 82.2 million children between the ages six to fourteen are not in the school. The people who pursue education drops out in the early stage due to poverty. Cast and gender discrimination irrelevant education and lack of education facilities. Dalits were less educated for centuries; they were suffered from low rate of literacy and primary education. This has been resulted in social, cultural, and economic supuration of Dalit, though the Government of India initiative through positive affirmation by providing reservation.

Education empowers Dalit.

Social development is one of the most crucial sectors .even after more than seven decades of independence, the situations remain unchanged. It is an impossible task to empower them without education because there is no other tool which can be applied to develop the depressed people. when the situations were completely adverse for these people before independence.

Dr B.R. Ambedkar achieved the highest degree of academic excellence. He receives doctorate in economics from Columbia University. It was considered the biggest achievement for all the Dalit community. The reservation has been provided by the constitution to them. It is helpful for them in education as well as in employment too. At present several people utilizing opportunity. However, the opportunity or empowerment of Dalit is not uniform because still they are facing torment, but the things are not at surface level. In rural areas they are not treated well.

There is a rule applied everywhere for changing something, it never takes place in a brief time. Only political changes take place soon due to the support of politician and upper-class people. There are some great personalities like Vivekananda who always propagate equality in the society. He fought against castes and always suggested that education is the primary tool to subside inequality from society. Education is very essential to the community in the absence of it; Dalit empowerment is merely will be a dream. They must be provided access to higher education. It helps to develop their identity in the caste conscious society. It is the medium to transform their life from bottom to the top. The major problem in the process is finance for higher studies. Now government runs the number of schemes regarding the issue.

Conclusion:

India is the most prominent civilization of the world. In Indian history starting twenty-five years were fixed to get education. At international level education is always first to empower the human being, except education no other ways is

there to enhance the personality of them. They were subjugated since long time. They were excluded from the number of rights like right to education, right to speak, right against exploitation. It is said that education is potentially a powerful factor to empowerment. So, Dalit should be motivated to get education. Some of them are empowering themselves. So, it is their duty to support to those people who are still in darkness.

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